

ZKI Top Trends Survey 2026

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Technical Documentation

This document contains the technical documentation for the applications developed for the 2026 Top Trends Survey: the Survey Analyzer for data processing and analysis, and the Dashboard application for interactive presentation of results. It is intended for developers and interested parties who wish to use similar applications or are planning such applications.

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Introduction

The Strategy and Organization Working Group of the ZKI Association conducts an annual survey on the key topics and priorities of its member institutions. The aim is to regularly capture and document the central issues facing IT departments at universities and research institutions. The survey targets CIOs, directors of computing centers, IT directors, and individuals in comparable roles.

Survey Structure

The survey consists of two parts: a core survey with recurring questions and annually changing focus questions on current key topics. The core survey forms the backbone of the survey and, due to its continuity, enables year-over-year comparisons. In the past, it comprised twelve constant questions; for this year's edition, it has been revised, adapted to current issues, and streamlined to ten core questions.

The core survey captures a broad spectrum of current challenges and developments in the IT sector of universities. It inquires about defining top trends in IT and digitalization, as well as legal and regulatory requirements particularly relevant for 2026—such as in the areas of data protection, IT security, or accessibility. A dedicated focus is placed on IT security, capturing current challenges and key areas of activity. The use of AI solutions is also surveyed—both currently deployed applications and planned deployment scenarios. In the area of strategy and management, the current priorities of universities are assessed. Additionally, the survey identifies which technologies are gaining significance, which new services are being introduced, and which are expected to be replaced or discontinued. The question on IT governance examines the interplay between strategic and operational IT. Finally, it determines which skills and competencies IT organizations aim to build or strengthen by 2026.

Focus Questions 2026

This year's focus questions address the strategic positioning of university IT within the tension between technological autonomy, financial constraints, and institutional collaboration.

The thematic core is digital sovereignty: In light of increasing dependencies on global technology providers and intensified political debates concerning data protection, control, and European alternatives, the aim is to ascertain how universities interpret this concept and what concrete measures they undertake to preserve operational capacity and controllability.

Closely linked to this are the financial degrees of freedom. Strategic IT decisions require appropriate resources—whether for open-source solutions, European infrastructures, or the development of in-house competencies. Questions regarding budget development and cost control reveal the economic conditions under which universities can actually implement their IT strategies.

The third area, cooperation, completes the thematic arc: Digital sovereignty does not necessarily imply solitary efforts. Collaborative solutions, shared services, and the utilization of state or federal infrastructures can serve as pathways to strengthen independence from commercial providers while simultaneously using resources efficiently.

The three thematic areas are deliberately designed as a unified whole: they illustrate how universities can balance their IT between self-determination, cost-efficiency, and cooperation.

Results in Two Formats

Survey results are provided in two complementary formats. The interactive dashboard enables users to independently explore results and segmentations—response distributions can be filtered and compared by country, university type, and size; open-text clusters can be examined in detail, and thematic cross-references between questions can be traced. Accessible at

<https://hu.berlin/tt26>

In contrast, the evaluation documents provide an editorially prepared presentation: Each question is presented with diagrams and textual summaries that describe, interpret, and address relevant segment differences. The documents are available in German, French, and English.

Part I: Survey Analyzer

Overview

The survey evaluation application is a web-based system that imports multilingual survey data from CSV, Excel, and LimeSurvey structure files (LSS) and processes them through a multi-stage pipeline. During import, character encoding and delimiters are automatically detected; the LSS file additionally provides multilingual question texts and answer options. Subsequently, the system identifies the language of each open-text response (German, French, English) and translates foreign-language responses into German using LLM-based methods, preserving IT terminology, abbreviations, and product names unchanged. Combined open-text responses—e.g., “Moodle for teaching; BigBlueButton for video conferencing”—are decomposed into individual mentions via a hybrid strategy combining rule-based pattern recognition and LLM extraction, with automated quality validation.

The actual analysis distinguishes seven question types: single and multiple choice, yes/no matrices, Likert scales, rankings, cooperation matrices, and open-ended text questions. Open-ended responses are clustered thematically using LLMs, with trilingual labels and representative examples. The analysis mode—raw mode for narrative descriptions or item mode for enumerative answers—is configured per question. All results are segmented along up to three dimensions—country, university type, and size—including cross-filter combinations. For each segment, the system tests via chi-square and Cramér’s V whether statistically significant differences exist and performs pairwise comparisons between segments. A correlation analysis further identifies relationships between question pairs, while a thematic analysis assigns questions and clusters to overarching thematic areas such as AI, IT security, or cloud.

The results are exported in two formats: as structured Word reports in up to three languages, including graphics, LLM-generated question summaries (description, interpretation, segment differences), and country-specific free-text clusters, as well as JSON files for an interactive dashboard. The Word reports include an automatic table of contents and continuous page numbering. For significant segment differences and country comparisons, the system generates LLM-based interpretive texts using cautious, relativizing formulations. Detailed interactive exploration of segmented results is reserved for the dashboard.

In addition to the analysis pipeline, a Document Builder generates four publication documents (results report, survey evaluation, methodology documentation, technical documentation) in three languages each from Markdown source files. Texts are translated paragraph by paragraph via LLM and cached in a dedicated database table with change detection, ensuring only affected paragraphs are retranslated upon text modifications.

An interactive workbench allows clusters to be renamed, merged, or split retrospectively, extracted items to be reviewed, and responses to be moved between clusters. The entire

pipeline supports a resume mode for resuming interrupted processing, and a two-stage caching mechanism ensures that LLM results need not be recalculated in repeated runs.

Functional Documentation

1. Data Import

1.1 File Import

The system imports survey data from CSV and Excel files. For CSV files, character encoding and delimiters are detected automatically. For Excel files, a specific sheet can be selected; available sheets are displayed after upload.

After import, column names are automatically matched against the question configuration. Column names must exactly match the configuration; deviations will result in the affected question not being evaluated.

1.2 LimeSurvey Import

In addition to the data file, a LimeSurvey structure file (.lss) can be imported. It is parsed and provides multilingual question texts, answer options, and group structures to be incorporated into the configuration.

1.3 Language Detection

During import, the language is automatically detected for each response line. To do so, free-text columns are merged and analyzed using the langdetect library. German, French, and English are supported. Italian texts are assigned to the German-speaking evaluation group. For very short texts or errors, German is assumed as default. The result is stored per line in a language column.

1.4 Data Preview

After import, the interface displays a summary: filename, file type, number of rows and columns, import ID, and the result of column validation.

2. Configuration

2.1 YAML Editor

The question configuration can be edited directly in the interface. The integrated YAML editor displays the current configuration and allows modifications to question types, column assignments, labels, and report groups. Changes take effect immediately upon saving.

2.2 Question Types

Each question is assigned to one of the seven supported types:

Type	Description	Example
Single selection	Exactly one answer from	'What type of university?'

	given options	
Multiple selection	Multiple answers possible	'What tools do you use?'
Multiple selection binary	Yes/No matrix for multiple items	'Do you use the following services?'
Matrix/Likert	Rating multiple items on a scale	'Rate the relevance (1–5)'
Ranking	Ranking items	'Rank by priority'
Free text	Open text answer	'What challenges do you see?'
Cooperation matrix	Multidimensional rating matrix	'How important are the following partners?'

2.3 Report Groups

Questions are organized into thematic groups (e.g., “General Information,” “Governance Model,” “Focus Topic”). Grouping determines the sequence and structure in the Word export and dashboard.

3. Translation

3.1 Automatic Response Translation

Free-text responses in French and English can be automatically translated into German to enable consistent analysis. The translation is LLM-based and considers the higher education IT context: English technical terms (Cloud, Backup, Server), IT abbreviations (KI, AI, SIEM, API), product names (VMware, Moodle, SAP), laws (GDPR, AI Act), and established terms (Homeoffice, E-Mail) remain untranslated.

3.2 Speech Recognition

The translation component uses a two-stage language recognition, which is more accurate than import recognition:

- Keyword-based analysis with weighted hits (word lists, phrases, special characters)
- langdetect as fallback for ambiguous results

3.3 Review and Processing

Translated texts can be reviewed in an editable table and manually corrected if necessary. Corrections are saved in the database.

3.4 Caching

Each translation is cached both in the database and in memory. Previously translated texts are loaded immediately from the cache upon reoccurrence, without invoking the LLM again.

4. Item Extraction

4.1 Purpose

Many free text responses contain multiple mentions in a single text. Item extraction breaks down such combined responses into individual, atomic mentions to enable a more differentiated cluster analysis. Questions whose clustering mode is set to raw in the configuration are excluded from item extraction (see section 5.7).

Example:

- Input: 'We use Moodle for teaching; BigBlueButton for video conferencing.'
- Result: 'Moodle for teaching' + 'BigBlueButton for video conferencing.'

4.2 Rule-Based Extraction

The first stage identifies structural patterns in the text and extracts items based on delimiters:

Pattern	Recognition logic	Confidence
Single naming	Short text without separators	1.0
Line breaks	Lines beginning with a capital letter, no comma continuation	0.95
Semicolons	Semicolon separation with substantial parts	0.90
Dashes	Bulleted list at the beginning of the line	0.85
Numbering	Inline numbered lists (1. ... 2. ... 3. ...)	0.85
Comma lists	Comma lists with conjunction (A, B and C)	0.80
Fallback	No structure recognised	0.50

4.3 LLM Extraction

For texts where rule-based extraction is uncertain, an LLM-based extraction is available in two modes:

Syntactic mode: Conservative – only separates words where there is a clear syntactic separation.
Basic rule: 'When in doubt, do NOT separate.'

Thematic Mode (Default): Separates different topics or concepts but retains full context for each item. Example: "AI for Helpdesk and Cloud Migration" → 2 items instead of 1, each with complete description.

4.4 Validation and Retry

Each LLM extraction undergoes automated quality validation: a second LLM call checks whether the extracted items fully preserve the original's meaning. Validation assesses lost details (purpose, timeframe, target groups), excessive abstraction, and standalone comprehensibility. Negative validation triggers a retry with explicit feedback on the prior error.

4.5 Traceability

For each extracted item, the extraction method used, the confidence, the original text, and, in the case of LLM extraction, the model's rationale are stored.

5. Analysis

5.1 Single Choice

Frequency count of all responses. Results are displayed as percentages (relative to the number of valid responses) and sorted by predefined or alphabetical order.

5.2 Multi-Choice

Each selected option is counted and displayed as a share of respondents. Since each person may select multiple options, the sum of percentages may exceed 100%.

5.3 Multi-Choice Binary

For a series of items, the respective yes and no proportions are calculated. The display shows the yes proportion per item.

5.4 Matrix/Likert

For each item, the distribution across scale points is calculated and visualized as a 100% stacked bar. Additionally, the mean value per item is displayed.

5.5 Ranking

Items are evaluated using a weighted point system: For n ranks, rank 1 receives n points, rank 2 receives n-1 points, and so on. Results are sorted by weighted total score. Additionally, the average rank per item is calculated.

5.6 Cooperation Matrix

Multidimensional evaluation matrix for cooperation partners. For each partner, a weighted importance score is calculated, along with the distribution across the evaluation scale (e.g., "Very important" to "No cooperation"). Results are displayed as 100% stacked bars and as a heatmap.

5.7 Free Text Clustering

Free text responses are grouped into thematic clusters by an LLM. The clusters are given trilingual names (DE/FR/EN) and representative examples. Two analysis modes are available:

Raw mode: Each original response is assigned to a cluster as a whole. One response = one respondent = one cluster. Percentages refer to the total number of respondents.

Items mode: Previously extracted individual items are clustered. One person can be represented in several clusters. The percentages are based on the unique respondents per cluster and may exceed 100% in total.

The mode is controlled per question via the configuration key `clustering.mode`: `auto` (default) uses items if extracted individual items are available, otherwise raw mode; `raw` enforces raw mode. Item mode is suitable for enumerative questions ('Name...') in which respondents list independent items. Descriptive questions ('Describe...') require raw mode, as the atomisation of related descriptions destroys the context. In addition, an optional `clustering.hint` can be configured to specify question-specific differentiation dimensions. The hint is injected into the main, retry and sub-clustering prompts and helps the LLM to form meaningful subgroups even with thematically homogeneous responses (e.g. when all respondents write about governance structures).

6. Segmentation

6.1 Segmentation Dimensions

The results can be segmented along three dimensions:

Dimension	Examples
Country	Germany, Austria, Switzerland
Type of institution	University, technical college
Size	Small, medium, large

6.2 Thresholds

Segments with fewer than 5 cases are generally excluded from presentation to prevent identification of individual institutions. Segments with fewer than 10 cases receive a warning regarding low case count.

6.3 Cross Filtering

In addition to simple segmentations, combined segmentations are also supported:

- **Two-way combinations:** e.g., Country × University type (Germany + University)
- **Three-way combinations:** e.g., Country × University type × Size

Combinations falling below the configured minimum n are automatically excluded.

7. Significance Tests

7.1 Chi-Square Test

For each question, it is tested whether the response distributions differ statistically significantly between segments. The test is based on the chi-square test of independence using contingency tables (segments × response categories). The significance level is $\alpha = 0.05$.

7.2 Effect Size

Practical significance is measured using Cramér's V:

Cramér's V	Interpretation
< 0.1	Weak
0.1 – 0.3	Medium
≥ 0.3	Strong

A warning is issued if more than 20% of cells have expected frequencies below 5.

7.3 Pairwise Comparisons

In addition to the overall test, pairwise comparisons between all segments are conducted (e.g., Germany vs. Austria, Germany vs. Switzerland, Austria vs. Switzerland). Results are considered exploratory, as no correction for multiple testing is applied.

8. Correlation Analysis

8.1 Overview

The correlation analysis calculates relationships between all pairs of correlatable questions using the chi-square test and Cramér's V. Since only categorical data can be processed, the various question types are transformed in advance.

8.2 Data Conversion

Question type	Conversion
Single choice	Direct use of response values
Multiple choice	Number of items selected → 5 engagement groups (none, single, few, medium, many)
Matrix/Likert	Row mean → 3 groups (low, medium, high)
Ranking	Top 1 ranking as category

Free text	Cluster assignment
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8.3 Effect Size Classification

For the correlation analysis, a finer scale is used than in the segment tests:

Cramér's V	Interpretation
< 0.1	Negligible (not reported)
0.1 – 0.3	Weak
0.3 – 0.5	Medium
≥ 0.5	Strong

8.4 Filtering

Pairs of questions with fewer than 20 shared data points, categories with fewer than 5 entries, non-significant results, and suspiciously high correlations ($V > 0.95$, indicating artifacts) are excluded. Per topic group, a maximum of 5 correlations are reported; across topics, a maximum of 10.

9. Topic Analysis

9.1 Predefined Topics

The system operates with 8 predefined topics (e.g., AI, IT security, cloud, digital sovereignty). Each topic includes a description and an initial keyword list.

9.2 Keyword Extraction

Questions and clusters are assigned to topics using keywords. Keyword extraction is hybrid:

Rule-based: Regex-based search for keywords in question texts and answers.

LLM-supported (optional): The LLM generates additional topic-related keywords, taking into account the specific set of questions. Variants and synonyms are also recorded (e.g. 'AI', 'artificial intelligence', 'KI').

9.3 Topic Assignment

Questions and free-text clusters are assigned to topics based on their keywords. A question may be assigned to multiple topics. Assignments are persisted in the database and used in the dashboard as a thematic navigation structure.

10. Workbench

10.1 Cluster Processing

In the cluster workbench, the automatically generated clusters can be interactively refined:

- **Rename cluster:** Adjust multilingual names
- **Merge clusters:** Combine two clusters into one
- **Split cluster:** Divide one cluster into two new ones
- **Move responses:** Shift individual responses from one cluster to another
- **Re-cluster:** Fully re-run cluster analysis for a question

10.2 Item Management

The Item Workbench enables the review and editing of extracted items:

- **Item Overview:** Table of all extracted items with original text, extraction method, and confidence
- **Edit Items:** Correct or remove individual items
- **Find Similar Items:** Identify items with similar wording for potential merging
- **Reassign:** Automatically reassign items to appropriate clusters after cluster changes (LLM-based)

10.3 Normalization

Tools for standardizing responses:

- **Normalize spellings:** Standardize different spellings of the same term
- **Expand abbreviations:** Replace abbreviations with full terms

11. Export

11.1 Dashboard Export

Generates JSON files for the dashboard frontend. The data include all analysis results with stable keys, segmented outcomes, trilingual labels, and cluster examples. Optionally, country-specific cluster comparisons with LLM-generated comparison texts are added.

11.2 Word Export (Survey Analysis)

Generate a structured report as a Word document (.docx), organized according to the configured report groups. The export is created in up to three languages (DE, FR, EN) and includes:

- Title page and table of contents (depth configurable per document, default: levels 1–2)
- Part 1: Overall charts per question with LLM-generated summaries (description, interpretation, segment differences)

- Part 2: Country-specific topics with free-text clusters and representative examples
- Footer displaying “Page x of y” in the respective document language

The segment analysis is presented exclusively as a textual summary in Part 1. Detailed interactive exploration of segmented results is conducted via the dashboard.

11.3 LLM Summaries

For each question, a three-part LLM summary is generated and inserted into the Word report after the graphics:

1. **Description of results:** Factual presentation of data (e.g., most frequent responses, distributions)
2. **Interpretation:** Contextualization and highlighting of notable patterns
3. **Segment differences:** Details are provided only for statistically significant differences; otherwise: standard phrase “No clear differences between segments can be derived.”

The texts are generated in a factual-academic tone (Open Science context). For segment analysis, chi-square tests are calculated per segment dimension. Summaries are generated in German and subsequently translated into French and English. All results are cached in the database.

11.4 Segment Insights

For significant segment differences, LLM-based interpretation texts are generated. These employ cautious, qualifying formulations (hedging) and avoid causal statements or generalizations. For each question, both an individual finding per significant difference and a summary interpretation are produced.

11.5 Publication Documents (Document Builder)

Regardless of the analysis pipeline, four publication documents can be created in each of three languages:

Document	Target group	Contents
Survey evaluation	Researchers, decision-makers	Summaries, top trends, focus questions, country comparisons and complete individual question evaluation
Method documentation	Open science	Survey design, LLM methodology, prompt documentation
Technical documentation	Developers	Analyser and dashboard documentation

The documents are assembled from Markdown source files maintained in a configurable directory (`docs/de/`). A central configuration file (`config/documents.yaml`) defines for each document its components, title, subtitle, and purpose description in three languages. Shared components (cover, introduction, top trends, focus questions, summary, country comparison) are defined as `shared_sections` and included in documents via reference (`shared:key`).

All documents receive a uniform cover with document-specific placeholders (subtitle, purpose, Zenodo DOI), a shared introductory text, and a table of contents (depth configurable per document, default: 2 levels). The survey evaluation is treated as a special case: the DOCX file generated by the pipeline is loaded, and via `prefix_sections`, cover, introduction, top trends, focus questions, summary, and country comparison are prepended; additional sections can be appended via `suffix_sections`.

Translation is performed paragraph by paragraph using an LLM, with the source text provided as context. Each translation is stored in a separate database table with a hash of the source text. Only affected paragraphs are retranslated upon text changes.

The Document Builder offers two modes:

- **Full build:** Rebuilds all documents in all languages
- **Update:** Builds only documents whose source files have changed since the last export

12. Complete Pipeline

12.1 Batch Execution

All processing steps can be executed in a single pass via a central pipeline function. The interface provides configuration options for:

- Activation/deactivation of optional steps (translation, item extraction, topic analysis, correlation analysis, LLM summaries, Word export)
- Selection of export languages
- Deep vs. quick topic analysis
- Target directory for output files

12.2 Progress Indicator

During processing, progress is displayed in the interface: current step, number of processed questions, estimated remaining time, and status messages.

12.3 Resume Mode

In case of interruption or error, the pipeline can be resumed at the point of interruption. Already successfully processed questions are skipped. This is particularly relevant for large surveys with many LLM calls, where total processing may take several hours.

13. Multilingualism

The system is consistently designed in three languages (German, French, English):

Area	Multilingual
Question texts and labels	Configurable in DE/FR/EN
Answer options	Configurable in DE/FR/EN
Cluster names	Automatically generated in three languages
Cluster examples	Automatically translated into all three languages
Correlation interpretations	Generated in three languages
Insight texts	Generated in German, automatically translated
Question summaries	Generated in German, automatically translated into FR/EN
Publication documents	Translated paragraph by paragraph with context prompt and DB cache
Word reports	One separate document per language
Dashboard data	All labels and texts in three languages

14. Database Status

The interface continuously displays the current status of the database:

- Number of stored imports
- Number of analyzed questions and segments
- Number of saved translations and clusters
- Number of extracted items
- Number of cached question summaries
- Number of cached document translations
- Schema version and file size

Technical Documentation

System Architecture

1.1 Overview

The Survey Analyzer is a web-based application for automated analysis of multilingual survey data. Its architecture follows a pipeline pattern, processing data step by step from raw input to final export. The user interface is built on Gradio 6 and runs as a local web application. Processing is performed server-side in Python.

1.2 Components

The system consists of four main layers:

Presentation Layer: The Gradio-6 interface provides eight main tabs (Import, Configuration, Item Extraction, Analysis, Workbench, Export, Topics, Info). The Workbench contains three sub-tabs for cluster editing, item management, and normalization. The Export tab includes not only single-question and full exports but also the Document Builder for publication documents.

Processing layer: Specialized handlers process the seven supported question types. Additional modules handle translation, item extraction, clustering, segmentation, statistical tests, correlation analysis, and topic analysis. The Document Builder assembles Markdown source files into Word documents and translates them paragraph by paragraph.

LLM Integration Layer: All LLM calls route through a unified client accessing an OpenAI-compatible API. The backend is interchangeable (vLLM, Ollama, OpenAI API, Azure OpenAI). Each task (translation, extraction, clustering, insights, document translation) uses task-specific prompts and parameters.

Persistence layer: An SQLite database (schema version 6 with automatic migrations) stores all import data, analysis results, translations, cluster assignments, question summaries, topic mappings, and document translations. A two-stage caching mechanism (database + in-memory) accelerates repeated LLM calls.

1.3 Processing Pipeline

The pipeline consists of up to nine consecutive steps:

```
Import → Translation* → Item extraction* → Analysis → Topic analysis* → Correlation analysis* → LLM summaries* → Word export* → Dashboard export
```

* = optional

Regardless of the analysis pipeline, the Document Builder can assemble, translate, and export publication documents from Markdown sources as Word files.

Resume mode allows resuming interrupted processes. Completed questions are skipped unless explicit recalculation is requested. Progress is reported to the interface via callbacks.

2. Input Formats

2.1 Survey Data

Format	Recognition	Requirements
CSV	Automatic delimiter and encoding recognition	Tabular structure
Excel .xlsx	Sheet selection via the interface	openpyxl
Excel .xls (Legacy)	Sheet selection via the interface	xlrd

Encoding detection (CSV): Sequential attempt of UTF-8, UTF-8-sig, Latin-1, CP1252, and ISO-8859-1. The first successful encoding is used.

Delimiter Detection (CSV): Automatically via Python's CSV sniffing engine (semicolon, comma, tab, etc.).

The columns of the imported file are validated against the question configuration. Column names must exactly match the configuration. Each row corresponds to a respondent.

2.2 LimeSurvey Structure File

Format	Components	Purpose
.lss (XML)	LimeSurvey export file	Multilingual question texts, answer options, question structure

The LSS file is parsed and supplements the YAML configuration with multilingual labels, answer options, and question group assignments.

2.3 Configuration Files

File	Format	Contents
Question configuration	YAML	Question types, column mappings, labels (DE/FR/EN), report groups, sort orders
Translation table	YAML	Static translations for UI elements and answer categories
Topic definitions	YAML	Predefined topics with

		keywords and descriptions
Document configuration	YAML	Parts list for publication documents, Zenodo DOIs, multilingual metadata
Dashboard navigation	JSON	Navigation structure of the dashboard

The question configuration is the central control element: it defines for each question the type, associated columns, multilingual labels, answer options, and assignment to report groups.

2.4 Markdown Source Files

For the Document Builder, the texts of the publication documents are maintained as Markdown files in a configurable directory (default: `docs/de/`). The files use standard Markdown formatting (headings, bold, italic, lists) and are assembled into documents via the document configuration.

3. Output Formats

3.1 Dashboard Export (JSON)

Three JSON files form the data basis of the dashboard:

`dashboard_data.json`: Contains all analysis results with stable, language-independent keys (from v1.6). Per question: overall results, segmented results for all segment combinations (1-way, 2-way, 3-way), free-text clusters with segmented frequencies and trilingual examples.

`themes.json`: Theme assignments with keywords, question mappings, and cluster mappings per theme.

`correlations.json`: Significant correlations between question pairs with Cramér's V, effect size classification, and multilingual interpretation texts.

Optional: **`country_clusters.json`** with country-specific cluster comparisons and LLM-generated insight texts.

3.2 Word Export (DOCX)

Structured report in up to three languages (DE, FR, EN):

Contents	Content
Title page	Survey title, year, language
Table of contents	Automatically generated (depth configurable per document, default: levels 1–2)
Part 1: Overall evaluations	Results by report groups: graphic, LLM summary (description, interpretation,

	segment differences)
Part 2: Country-specific topics	Free text clusters by country with representative examples
Footer	'Page x of y' in the respective document language

Graphic Formats: All charts are embedded in the report as PNG images. Horizontal bar charts, 100% stacked bar charts, heatmaps, treemaps, and small-multiples grids are used.

3.3 Publication Documents (DOCX)

The Document Builder generates four publication documents in each of three languages:

Document	Contents	Source
Survey evaluation	Complete evaluation of individual questions with introductory summaries, top trends, focus questions and country comparisons	Pipeline-generated DOCX + Markdown prefix sections
Method documentation	Survey design, evaluation procedures, prompt documentation	Markdown files
Technical documentation	Analysers and dashboard documentation	Markdown files

All publication documents receive a uniform cover (with document-specific subtitle and purpose description), a common introductory text, a table of contents (depth configurable per document via `toc_max_level`, default: 2 levels), and a footer with page numbers.

3.4 Additional Outputs

Format	Contents
SQLite database	All interim and final results, Schema v6
PNG graphics	Individual charts as image files

4. Database

4.1 Schema (Version 6)

The SQLite database stores the complete analysis state:

Area	Stored data
Import	Raw data, file name, timestamp, import ID

Analysis	Results per question and segment, cluster assignments
Translation	Translation cache for survey content (original, source language, target language → translation)
Item extraction	Extracted items with method, confidence, original text, LLM justification
Clustering	Cluster definitions, trilingual names, examples, response assignments
Topics	Topic definitions, keyword mappings, question/cluster assignments
Question summaries	Description, interpretation, segment text per question/language (cache)
Document translations	Paragraph-by-paragraph translation cache for publication documents with change detection (hash)

Migrations: At startup, the system checks the schema version and automatically performs migrations (v1 → v2 → v3 → v4 → v5 → v6).

4.2 Document Translation Cache

The table `document_translations` stores translations of publication documents separately from survey translations:

Field	Description
<code>document_id</code>	Document key (e.g. 'survey_analysis')
<code>section_file</code>	Source file (e.g. 'methodology_text.md')
<code>paragraph_index</code>	Paragraph number within the file
<code>source_hash</code>	SHA-256 hash of the source text (16 characters)
<code>translated_text</code>	Translated text

The system automatically detects whether a source paragraph has changed via the `source_hash`. Only modified paragraphs are re-translated during an update. Translations can be selectively deleted per document and language.

4.3 Caching Strategy

Cache level	Scope	Purpose
Database cache	Persistent across sessions	Translations, cluster results, item extractions
Document cache	Persistent across sessions	Paragraph-by-paragraph

		translations with change detection
In-memory cache	Current session	Quick access to frequently used translations
Resume mode	Pipeline runs	Skip questions that have already been analysed

5. LLM Integration

5.1 API Configuration

Parameters	Description	Standard
Base URL	API endpoint	http://localhost:11434/v1
Model	Model name	Configurable
API key	Authentication	Empty for local backends
Temperature	Creativity parameters	0.3
Max tokens	Maximum response length	4096
Timeout	Time limit per request	300 seconds

5.2 Task-Specific Parameters

Task	Temperature	Max Tokens	Note
Translation	0.1	2000	Low for precision
Item extraction	0.1	2000	Low for consistency
Item validation	0.1	500	Short yes/no answers
Clustering	0.6 (+0.15 bei Retry)	8192	Higher for cluster diversity
Sample translation	0.1	2000	In the clustering post-processing step
Insight generation	0.5–0.6	200–400	Carefully worded interpretation texts
Question summary	0.2	2000	JSON: description, interpretation, segments
Document translation	0.3	4000	Paragraph by paragraph with background text as context
Keyword extraction	Standard	Standard	For topic analysis

5.3 Error Handling

All LLM calls are embedded in try-catch blocks. For JSON outputs, responses are scanned via regex for JSON structures and robustly parsed. Clustering allows a maximum of three attempts; with each retry, temperature is increased. Dominant clusters exceeding a configurable threshold are automatically split into subgroups. Failed LLM calls trigger fallback values (e.g., original text for translation errors, individual listing for extraction failures).

6. Dependencies

6.1 Python Libraries

Bibliothek	Version	Usage
pandas	≥ 2.0	Data processing
numpy	≥ 1.24	Numerical calculations
scipy	≥ 1.10	Statistical tests (chi-square)
httpx	≥ 0.24	HTTP client for LLM API
python-docx	≥ 0.8.11	Word export
docxcompose	≥ 1.4	Merging Word documents (Document Builder)
matplotlib	≥ 3.7	Diagram generation
pyyaml	≥ 6.0	YAML configuration
langdetect	≥ 1.0.9	Language recognition
gradio	≥ 6.0	Web user interface
openpyxl	≥ 3.1	Excel .xlsx import
xlrd	≥ 2.0.1	Excel .xls import (legacy)

Optional: squarify (treemap visualization)

6.2 Infrastructure

Component	Technology
Runtime environment	Python 3.11+
Database	SQLite 3 (file-based)
LLM backend	Any OpenAI-compatible endpoint
Operation	Local execution or server deployment

7. Configuration Structure

7.1 Question Configuration (YAML)

The central configuration defines the survey structure:

```
settings:
  survey_metadata:
    survey_year: 2026
    survey_title:
      de: "Umfrage-Titel"
      fr: "Titre de l'enquête"
      en: "Survey Title"
  report_groups:
    group_id:
      order: 1
      label: {de: "...", fr: "...", en: "..."}
      questions: [question_id_1, question_id_2]

questions:
  question_id:
    type: single_choice | multi_choice | multi_choice_binary |
          matrix_likert | ranking | freetext | cooperation_matrix
    columns: ["spalte_1", "spalte_2"]
    label: {de: "...", fr: "...", en: "..."}
    options: {de: ["Opt 1", "Opt 2"], fr: [...], en: [...]}
    sort_order: ["Opt 1", "Opt 2"]
    clustering:          # nur für freetext
      mode: auto | raw   # auto = Items wenn vorhanden, raw = Vollantworten
      hint: "..."      # optional: fragenspezifische Differenzierungsdimensionen
```

7.2 Document Configuration (YAML)

The file `config/documents.yaml` controls the Document Builder:

```
zenodo:
  de: "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.XXXXXXXX"
  en: "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.XXXXXXXX"
  fr: "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.XXXXXXXX"

source_dir: "docs/de"
translation_context: "introduction.md"

shared_sections:
  cover: cover.md
  introduction: introduction.md
  focus: Fokusfragen.md
  countries: Laendervergleich.md
  toptrends: TopTrends.md
  summary: Zusammenfassung.md

documents:
  survey_analysis:
    existing_docx:
```

```

    de: "outputs/.../report_de_...docx"
  prefix_sections:
    - shared:cover
    - shared:introduction
    - shared:toptrends
    - shared:focus
    - shared:summary
    - shared:countries
  toc_max_level: 3

methodology:
  filename: "TT26_Methodendokumentation"
  sections:
    - shared:cover
    - shared:introduction
    - "methodology_text.md"
    - "methodology_prompts.md"

```

Each document defines its components as a list of Markdown files or references to shared building blocks (`shared:cover`, `shared:introduction`, `shared:focus`, etc.). For survey evaluation, a pre-generated DOCX file is referenced instead of Markdown; `prefix_sections` prepend components (cover, introduction, top trends, focus questions, summary, country comparison), while `suffix_sections` may append additional ones. The depth of the table of contents is configurable per document via `toc_max_level` (default: 2).

7.3 Segmentation

The segmentation dimensions are defined in the configuration:

Dimension	configuration key	Typical values
Land	country	Germany, Austria, Switzerland
type of university	institution_type	university, technical college
Size	size	Small, Medium, Large

7.4 Environment Variables

The LLM connection and additional runtime parameters are configured via a `.env` file.

Part II: Dashboard

Overview

The dashboard visualizes the results of the ZKI Top Trends survey on higher education IT as an interactive web application. Survey results can be explored across seven viewing modes: chronologically by question sequence, thematically grouped (e.g., AI, IT security, cloud, governance), as statistical correlation analysis between questions (maps, heatmaps, or network graphs), and as a country comparison highlighting nation-specific deviations from overall results. A summary page provides an editorial overview of key findings.

Results can be filtered by country, university type, and institution size—either as single filters via the sidebar or as combined multi-select filters in the “My University” view, which generates a comparative display between overall results and filtered selection. Depending on question type, different chart formats are used: horizontal bar charts, Likert stacked bars, ranking charts, and AI-supported cluster analyses for open-text responses with expandable details and sample answers. All charts are exportable as images.

The entire application is trilingual (German, French, English), works online and offline, and supports deep-linking via URL hash, enabling direct linking or bookmarking of specific views.

Function Documentation

1. Overview

The dashboard enables interactive exploration of the ZKI Top Trends survey results on higher education IT. It targets CIOs, IT managers, and researchers seeking to analyze and compare survey outcomes across various dimensions. The application is trilingual (German, French, English) and operates both online and offline.

2. View Modes

The dashboard provides seven view modes, accessible via the main navigation bar.

2.1 Overview (Home)

The homepage displays a language-dependent header image, key metrics (participants, countries, number of questions, survey period), and an introduction to the survey. From here, users can directly navigate to the analysis or download the publication.

2.2 Summary

An editorial overview of the survey's key findings. This section serves as a narrative introduction prior to detailed data exploration.

2.3 All Questions

Chronological display of all survey questions, grouped by survey structure categories (General Information, Governance Model, Changes from Previous Year, Focus Topic, Core Survey). Each question is presented as a card with question text, question type badge, sample size, and corresponding chart.

2.4 By Themes

The questions are grouped into thematic areas (e.g., Artificial Intelligence, IT Security, Cloud Computing, Digital Sovereignty, Collaborations, Budget, IT Services, IT Governance). Topics are displayed as tab navigation, each with an icon and brief description. Upon switching, the associated charts are automatically re-rendered.

2.5 Correlations

Statistical correlation analysis between survey questions in three presentation formats:

- **Map View** – Individual correlations displayed as cards with Cramér's V, p-value, strength badge, and interpretation, categorized into topic-specific and cross-topic correlations.
- **Heatmap** – Correlation matrix of all significant relationships using a color scale.
- **Network** – Force-directed network visualizing questions as nodes and correlations as edges.

A strength filter (all/strong/medium/weak) is available in all three views.

2.6 Country Comparison

Comparison of survey results by country with focus on open-text cluster data:

- **Cluster Comparison** – Displays the percentage cluster shares per country for each question.
- **Deviations** – Identifies, per country, the largest deviations from the overall result. A configurable threshold (default: 10%) filters only significant differences.

2.7 My University (My Profile)

Personalized filter view with multi-select filters for country, university type, and size. Multiple values per dimension can be selected. Results are displayed as a comparative view: overall result alongside filtered result. Demographic questions are hidden in this view, as they yield no meaningful insights when filtering is active.

3. Chart Types

3.1 Horizontal Bar Chart

Used for single-choice, multi-choice, and binary multiple selection. Sorting is automatic and context-dependent: Yes/No questions in fixed order with color coding, budget questions by trend direction, size questions in logical order, default descending by percentage. "Other" always appears at the end. Hover tooltips display absolute numbers.

3.2 Ranking Chart

Special display for ranking questions with weighted scores. Top 3 positions receive podium coloring (gold, silver, bronze).

3.3 Stacked Bar Chart (100%)

For Likert scales and matrix questions. Diverging color scale from red (strongly negative) through gray (neutral) to green (strongly positive). Each row represents an item; segments show response distribution.

3.4 Cluster Diagram

For open-text responses grouped by AI into thematic clusters. Displays clusters as bars with percentage and count. Expandable via an accordion showing cluster details (description and sample responses in the current language).

3.5 Comparison Chart

Double-bar display in the "My University" view. Each response option is shown with two bars: overall result (semi-transparent) and filtered result (solid color).

3.6 Small Multiples

Expandable comparison charts below each question. Display result distribution segmented by all available categories (country, university type, size). Available only for questions with segmented data.

4. Filter Functions

4.1 Global Sidebar Filter

In the left sidebar, a single filter can be set: filter type (country, university type, or size) and a specific value. All charts then display only the data of the selected segment. The sample display shows the current n relative to the total n.

4.2 Multi-Select Cross Filter (My University)

Extended filtering with multiple selection per dimension via checkboxes. A "Select All" toggle is available per segment. Changes are only applied via an explicit "Apply" button; unapplied changes are visually indicated.

4.3 Minimum Sample Size

If $n < 5$, no chart is displayed; instead, a note indicates insufficient data. For $5 \leq n < 10$, a warning advises cautious interpretation.

5. Multilingualism

Three languages are supported: German, French, and English. Language selection is done via buttons in the header. The initial language is determined by the URL parameter, browser setting, or default (German).

The translation affects all levels: UI texts (navigation, buttons, hints), question texts and answer options, topic and group labels, as well as cluster descriptions and sample answers. Upon language switch, all charts are redrawn with translated labels.

6. URL Linking

The application state is stored in the URL hash. This allows specific views to be directly linked or saved as bookmarks—for example, a particular topic view in a specific language. Browser forward/back navigation is supported.

7. Diagram Export

Each chart can be exported as an image (PNG or SVG). The filename includes the question ID and the current language.

8. Responsive Behavior

On mobile devices, the sidebar appears as an overlay via a hamburger menu button, and navigation wraps onto multiple lines. On desktop, the sidebar is implemented as a fixed, collapsible side panel. All diagrams automatically adjust to the available width.

A print view hides navigation, sidebar, and interactive elements and inserts page breaks before question groups.

Technical Documentation

1. Technologies Used and Their Interaction

The dashboard is a client-side single-page application that runs entirely in the browser. Its architecture is based on the interplay of four core technologies:

Alpine.js provides the application framework. A single Alpine component (`dashboard()`) manages the entire application state—language, active filters, view mode, accordion states—and controls the visibility and content of all UI elements directly in HTML via reactive data binding (`x-show`, `x-text`, `x-bind`). When a state changes (e.g., filter switch), Alpine automatically updates all affected DOM elements and triggers re-rendering of the relevant charts via `$watch` and `$nextTick`.

Plotly.js generates all charts. Each chart function receives a DOM container, the question object with metadata, and the current result data. Plotly renders the charts as SVG into the container and handles responsiveness, hover tooltips, and image export (PNG/SVG).

D3.js is used exclusively for network visualization of correlations. A force-directed layout positions questions as nodes and correlations as edges, with node size and edge thickness reflecting statistical strength.

Tailwind CSS provides all styling via utility classes directly in HTML. An extended configuration defines brand colors and the DM Sans font. Responsive behavior (mobile sidebar as overlay, desktop as collapsible sidebar) is controlled via Tailwind breakpoints.

The data flow is strictly unidirectional: Alpine holds the state, computes the data to be displayed, and passes it to the chart functions. There is no build step – all libraries are loaded via CDN.

2. Loading Data and Operating Modes

The application supports two operating modes. In **server mode**, six JSON files are loaded in parallel via `fetch()` from a `data/` directory at startup. The two core files (survey data and topics) must load successfully; four additional files (survey structure, correlations, country clusters, segment insights) are optional and are silently ignored on failure.

If the fetch fails – typical with local `file://` access – the **offline mode** is activated: The application checks whether global JavaScript constants (`DASHBOARD_DATA`, `THEMES_DATA`, etc.) exist. These are generated by a build script from the JSON files and included as `<script>` tags. If these are also missing, an error message with a retry button is displayed.

Upon successful loading, the state is restored from the URL hash (language, view mode, active topic), the first topic is activated by default, and the initial charts are rendered.

3. Data Model

Central Data Structure

The main data is provided as a nested JSON object. The top level contains metadata (survey year, total number of participants), segment definitions, and a questions object containing all survey questions as key-value pairs.

Each question has a type (e.g., `single_choice`, `freetext`, `matrix_likert`), multilingual texts, answer options, and a `results` object. Results are structured hierarchically: `results.all` contains overall results (n, absolute values, percentages). `results.by_country`, `results.by_institution_type`, and `results.by_size` contain the same structures broken down by segment values. For cross-filters, combined keys such as `results.by_country_institution_type` exist, with value keys separated by | (e.g., `DE|university`).

Free Text Clusters

Free-text responses are grouped by AI into thematic clusters. Each cluster contains a multilingual name, a description, translated sample responses, and its own `results` structure with percentages and absolute numbers, also breakable down by segments.

Multilingual Fields

All textual content in the data uses a uniform language object { `"de": "...", "fr": "...", "en": "..."` }. Response options additionally support a legacy format with language arrays. The application checks both formats on every access and falls back to the German variant or the option ID.

4. Graph Generation

Dispatch Mechanism

When rendering a question, `renderChart()` selects the appropriate chart function based on the question type. The container is located via an ID that varies depending on the view mode (different prefixes for question, topic, keyword, and profile views). Before rendering, it checks whether sufficient data is available ($n \geq 5$); otherwise, a placeholder is displayed.

Bar Charts (Single-/Multi-Choice)

The function `renderBarChart()` extracts labels and percentage values from the result data and applies context-dependent sorting. The sorting logic automatically detects:

- **Yes/No questions** – fixed order with semantic color coding (Green/Red/Orange)
- **Budget/trend questions** – ordered by direction (increase at top, decrease at bottom)

- **Size questions** – logical order (smallest at top)
- **Standard** – descending by percentage value, “Other” always at end

Since Plotly displays the first array element at the bottom for horizontal bars, the desired visual order is internally inverted. Color assignment is handled via `getSemanticColor()`, which automatically assigns appropriate colors based on multilingual keywords.

Labels are translated before display: first via the question’s `options` field, then via a fallback translation table. The left margin is dynamically adjusted to the longest label length.

Stacked Bar Charts (Likert/Matrix)

For Likert scales and matrix questions, `renderStackedBarChart()` generates 100% stacked bars with a diverging color scale (Red → Orange → Gray → Green). Each row represents an item; segments display the response distribution.

Ranking Charts

`renderRankingChart()` calculates weighted scores from rankings and displays the results with podium coloring (gold, silver, bronze for top 3).

Cluster Charts (Free Text)

`renderClusterChart()` displays AI-generated clusters as horizontal bars with percentage and absolute count, sorted in descending order by frequency. Below the chart, an accordion provides access to cluster details, including descriptions and translated example responses.

Comparison Charts

In the "My University" view, `renderComparisonChart()` generates double bars: the overall result (semi-transparent) next to the filtered result (solid color) enables direct visual comparison.

Small Multiples

`renderSmallMultiples()` generates compact comparison charts below a question, segmented by all available categories. For size segments, a logical sorting (small → large) is applied; for other segments, sorting is by case count.

5. Segmentation and Filter Logic

Simple Filter (Sidebar)

The sidebar filter allows selecting a single segment (country, university type, or size) with one value. Data is retrieved directly from the corresponding `results.by_<segment>.<value>`. If no segmented data exists for a question, the display automatically falls back to overall data.

Multi-Select Cross Filter (My University)

The "My University" view allows simultaneous selection of multiple values per segment. The filter logic operates in multiple stages:

4. **Combination Calculation:** All possible combinations are generated from the selected values. With two countries and one university type, two combinations result.
5. **Data Search with Fallback Hierarchy:** For each combination, the full cross-filter level is first searched (e.g., `by_country_institution_type["DE|university"]`). If unavailable, it falls back stepwise to smaller combinations: first pairwise, then single filters, finally overall data.
6. **Aggregation:** Results of all combinations are merged: absolute values are summed, percentages recalculated from aggregated values. Duplicates from fallback overlaps are avoided via unique keys.
7. **n Calculation:** Sample size is summed only from exact matches (no fallback). If exclusively fallbacks apply, n is set to 0, suppressing display.

Complex question types (open text, cooperation matrix, Likert) do not support cross-filter aggregation and instead use the single best matching filter with priority Land > university type > size.

Sample Thresholds

The application enforces minimum case numbers: No chart is displayed for $n < 5$. A warning appears for $5 \leq n < 10$. These thresholds apply consistently across all view modes.

6. Internationalization

Trilingualism (DE/FR/EN) spans four levels: UI texts via a central translation table, question texts and answer options directly in data objects, topic and structure labels in configuration files, and a fallback translation table for answer labels used when no option-level translation exists.

Language detection at startup first checks the URL parameter `?lang=`, then the browser language; default is German. When switching languages, the entire state is updated: Alpine re-renders UI texts, all charts are redrawn with translated labels, and the URL hash is updated.

7. Navigation and State Management

URL Hash-Based Navigation

The application state is stored as a URL hash (e.g., `#view=themes&lang=de&theme=ki`). View mode, language, and view-specific parameters (active theme, selected keyword, correlation subview) are saved. With each state change, the hash is updated via `history.pushState()`, enabling browser forward/back navigation.

Rendering Coordination

View changes trigger a cascade: Alpine updates view visibility, and after a brief timeout (100–200ms for DOM stability), charts of the new view are rendered. Watchers on `activeTheme`, `correlationView`, and `correlationStrengthFilter` ensure changes within a view are immediately reflected.

8. Correlation Analysis Visualization

The correlation data contain pairwise statistical relationships between questions, using Cramér's V as coefficient, p-value, and strength classification (strong/moderate/weak). The application provides three visualizations:

The **card view** iterates through the topic-grouped correlation structure and displays each correlation as a card with the involved questions, statistical metrics, and a multilingual interpretation.

The **heatmap** collects all correlations, constructs a symmetric matrix, and renders it as a Plotly heatmap with a color scale ranging from Weak to Medium to Strong.

The **network** uses D3 force simulation: questions are displayed as circles, correlations as connecting lines. The simulation positions highly correlated questions closer together. Nodes can be moved via drag.

All three views respect a common strength filter. The strength classification is normalized from various data formats (English and German labels are mapped to uniform values).